

Decoding Soil Microbial Functioning Under Forest and Agricultural Ecosystems Of Western Ghats

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Abstract

The Western Ghats (WG) is a global mega-diversity hotspot where soil microbial ecosystems are crucial drivers of biogeochemical cycles, nutrient cycling, and organic matter decomposition. Land use type plays a significant role in regulating microbial communities in these tropical soils. This research project aimed to unravel the complex nutrient solubilization activity of soil micro-organisms by conducting a comparative analysis of microbial functioning under forest and agricultural ecosystems within the WG region. A semi-systematic review procedure, guided by the PRISMA framework, utilized literature focusing on the WG states and key words such as "soil microbial function" and "nutrient solubilization". Thirty-nine appropriate research publications detailing microbial diversity and nutrient transformation were included in the final review. Comparative analysis confirmed that forest soils generally support richer microbial communities and higher biomass than agricultural soils. Fungal diversity, in particular, demonstrates the strongest decline in cultivated areas, often resulting in a lower Fungal-to-Bacterial (F:B) Ratio. Key identified microbes, such as species of *Micrococcus* and *Pantoea*, facilitate Phosphorous (P) solubilization by releasing organic acids. Nutrient bioavailability is driven by microbial genetic pathways, including genes for nitrogenase enzymes

(N fixation) and phosphatases (P hydrolysis, e.g., *phoA*, *phoD*). In conclusion, forest soils retain superior genetic potential and metabolic ability for nutrient cycling compared to managed agricultural lands. Understanding these genetic routes provides essential insights into soil fertility dynamics. Future research should utilize metagenomic and multi-omics approaches to describe active functional networks for developing targeted microbial bioinoculants.

Keywords: Western Ghats, Soil Microbial Function, Nutrient Solubilization, Land Use Change, Metagenomics, Genetic Pathways

Introduction

Located in the western region of the country, the state of Maharashtra has a total size of 308,000 km² (Economic Survey of Maharashtra 2024-25). Situated between 16° N and 22° N latitude and 72° E and 81° E longitude, it is the third largest state in India (Ratna, 2012). Geographically, the state is separated into three natural regions: 1) the Konkan region, which includes the state's coastal area; 2) the Sahyadri hills, also referred to as the Western Ghats region; and 3) the area of the Deccan plateau.

The Western Ghats (WG), a range of mountains that stretch along India's west coast, are one of the many natural treasures that the country is endowed with. In addition to being an ecologically and geologically significant region for the diversity of endemic plants and animals (Ghare et al., 2023), the Western Ghats are one of India's mega-diversity hotspots, spanning 140,000 km² area over 1,600 km that pass through the states of Kerala, Tamil Nadu, Karnataka, Goa, Maharashtra, and Gujarat (Kale et al., 2016). Along with Sri Lanka, the Western Ghats are recognized as one of the eight hotspots for biological diversity in the world, as well as UNESCO World Heritage Sites and an ecologically sensitive area due to their remarkably diverse ecosystem and endemism (Myers et al., 2000).

Featuring billions of bacteria, millions of fungi and other macro and microorganisms, soil is one of the most diverse microbial ecosystems on the planet. Filamentous bacteria are more prevalent in the spaces between soil particles than their unicellular counterparts because soil is a mixture of minerals and organic matter (Chen et al., 2022). In soils, actinobacteria are ubiquitous. They are in charge of the natural processes of biodegradation and biodeterioration. Because of their adaptability and demonstrated capabilities, scientists are now screening these organisms from unexplored niche environments to extract new compounds (Ibeyaima et al., 2018).

Heterogeneity in forest ecosystems is critical for biogeochemical cycles, and microbial communities play an important role in forest ecosystem function (Lladó et al., 2017). Because they are involved in a number of activities, including nutrient cycling, plant nutrient intake, and decomposition, forests enable the survival of numerous microbial species, which are essential to preserving ecological equilibrium. Bacteria are key players in the biogeochemical cycles and participate in the breakdown of dead plant biomass (Bani et al., 2018). Likewise, they also play a part in the many nutrient changes that occur in the soil. According to Kumar et al. (2015) soil microbial communities have a variety of influences on plant productivity, nutrient uptake and ecosystem functioning on both conventionally tilled and untilled soils. Land use coverings have been found to play a more significant role in regulating microbial communities in tropical soils than in many temperate environments.

Metagenomics is a rapidly developing topic within the field of genome sciences that seeks to characterize the composition, roles and dynamically coevolving interactions between microbial communities and their environments, even in unculturable samples (Franzosa et al., 2015). The primary objectives of any metagenome sequencing project are to completely characterize a community, including its taxonomic composition, relative abundance of various species, and genetic composition, which includes the quantity, functional ability, and intra-population and intra-species heterogeneity of its genes (Scholz et al., 2012).

Mineralization is nothing but conversion of organic forms of nutrients into inorganic form, which is the major plant utilizable form of nutrient. This process is usually facilitated by soil microbes through release of metabolic enzymes and organic acids. A major part of all the seventeen essential macro and micronutrients are present in organic form added through plant debris, micro and macro fauna remains. Most nutrients, including nitrogen, phosphorus and sulfur that are present in biological habitats are bound in organic compounds and have a limited ability to be bioavailable to plants. To depolymerize and mineralize organic forms of nitrogen, phosphorus and sulfur, plants depend on the growth of soil microorganisms such as bacteria and fungi (Mahala et al., 2020). Following this, the components of these microbial cells are released, either by protozoic predation or by cycling and cell lysis. As a result, the soil is enriched with inorganic nitrogen, phosphorus and sulfur molecules, especially ionic species like ammonium nitrate, phosphate, and sulfate, which are ideal plant nutrition sources (Kathpalia & Bhatla, 2018).

It is clear that there are complicated interactions between soil microbes and nutrient content of soils which are largely affected by the type of vegetation cover. Gaining a thorough comprehension of these interactions is essential to identify and characterise soil's ability to

solubilise the nutrient elements. Therefore, this research project has been formulated with an aim to unravel this complex nutrient solubilization activity of soil micro-organisms under forest and agriculture ecosystems with following major objectives:.

1. To generate the data of various nutrient solubilizing microbes identified under forest and agroecosystems of Western Ghats region of Maharashtra.
2. To identify different genetic and metabolic pathways involved in nutrient bioavailability through extensive literature review.
3. To reproduce comparative analysis showing the effect of vegetation cover on microbial diversity and associated soil functioning.

Methods

To conduct a thorough research on the proposed topic, a well-established semi systematic review procedure, guided by the PRISMA (Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses) framework was followed for the selection and exclusion of literature (Page et al., 2021). The proposed research considered the following inclusion and exclusion criterion for screening of papers.

Category	Inclusion	Exclusion
Region	Western Ghats, Maharashtra, Karnataka, Kerala, Tamil Nadu	Other geographical locations
Ecosystem	Forest, Agriculture	Agroforestry, horticulture, urban, industrial, pasture
Study type	Peer reviewed papers, empirical, grey literature, government reports, scientific papers, book chapters	Opinion pieces, predatory journals
Major outcomes	Soil microbial diversity and functions, nutrient solubilization, genetic and metabolic pathways of nutrient transformation	Unrelated soil functions and properties
Publication date	2000 onwards	Before 2000

Data source and screening: A thorough literature review will be conducted using digital research repositories such as Research Gate, Google Scholar, Science Direct, Pub Med, Public library of Sciences (PLoS) and Cross-ref. The search will focus on key words like: "Forest ecosystem", "agricultural ecosystem," "soil microbial function," "nutrient solubilization," "bioavailability," "Western Ghats," "Maharashtra, "genetic mechanism", "metabolic pathways", "soil microbial diversity", "mineralization", "microbial activity", "land use cover", "land use pattern", "soil

metagenomics”. Additionally, we looked over relevant research articles and the followed the method of citation chaining.

As the Western Ghat trail is shared between four states i.e., Maharashtra, Karnataka, Kerala and Tamil Nadu, the research experiments reported from these places were also derived in the search results as they share common climatic, topographic, geographic, overall vegetative features and transboundary locations. These can help improve the database for better outcomes. In the final stage of scrutiny, we will fine-tune our research to suit our expected outcomes and will give preference to qualitative studies focussing on existing information, emerging trends, novel technology usage including metagenomics, metabolomics, PLFA studies, land cover-based variation (Forest and agriculture), comparative analysis, etc.

PRISMA FLOW DIAGRAM

Studies were carefully examined in the second step, and those that had a clear scientific approach and made a substantial contribution to the reporting of microbial diversity and its involvement in nutrient transformation were selected. Subjective and opinion studies were further eliminated. About 47 studies were produced as a result. Our investigation was further limited to 39

appropriate research publications and other pertinent published data that was particular to the microbial diversity in India's Western Ghats. In order to simplify and organize the classification of numerous studies, we have organized the content according to the goals stated in the introduction.

Results

Climate and ecosystem variations in Western ghats

The Western Ghats' climate is greatly influenced by its distance from the equator and altitudinal gradient. The weather is tropical and humid. The climate in the north and south of the Western Ghats, which are at elevations of 1500–2000 m and above, is mild, with typical temperatures ranging from 20 to 24 °C. Rainfall in this area ranges from 3000 to 4000 mm on average, with a maximum of 9000 mm. Rainfall in the eastern part of the Western Ghats is relatively lower, ranging from 1000 to 2500 mm. The rainy season lasts all year in areas closer to the equator with lower annual rainfall, while the extended dry season follows areas with substantial rainfall (such as Maharashtra's northern districts). Significant diversity in living forms has been facilitated by the region's varied climate and geographic alignment (Shabeer Ali et al., 2023)

Tropical evergreen forests, dry deciduous forests, moist deciduous forests, sholas, scrub jungles, savannas, especially high rainfall savannas, peat bogs, and Myristica swamps are the main vegetation types found in the Western Ghats (Zhang et al., 2017). There are comparatively fewer studies on the microbial community and diversity than there are on the floral and faunal diversity research. The majority of this studies are conducted in the southern part of the Western Ghats, but less is known about the microbial population and diversity in the northern region of the Western Ghats (Ghare et al., 2023).

Microbial diversity in forest and agriculture ecosystems of Western Ghats

Including the bacterial population, there are currently only about 5000 known prokaryotic species, which amounts to little more than 1–10% of the estimated 3,00,000–1,000,000 prokaryotic species on Earth. Just 1% of the prokaryotic species that have been studied can be grown in a lab. There are currently close to 13,000 fungal species known to exist in the Western Ghats region. Though just 130 species of mycorrhizal fungi have been identified to date, it is estimated that 300,000 plant species in the Western Ghats itself have mycorrhizal associations (Shabeer Ali et al., 2023). Potential Plant growth promoting growth regulators, which can function as biofertilizers and biopesticides, are the most common rhizobacteria in the rhizospheres of *Rauwolfia* spp. in WG areas (S. P. Kumar et al., 2014). An overview of the microbial species that

have been identified thus far from various places in the Western Ghat region is provided in the following table. This species' significant contribution to the cycling of nutrients has also been noticed:

Identified microbial species	Role in nutrient cycling	Location	Reference
<i>Cynobacteria</i> species such as, <i>Westiellopsis prolifica</i> Janet and <i>Nostoc calcicola</i> Brebsson ex Born. et Flah, <i>Nostoc</i> , <i>Anabaena</i> , <i>Chroococcus</i> . <i>Myxosarcina spectabilis</i> Geitler.	Atmospheric nitrogen (N) fixation	Western ghats of Maharashtra	(Nikam T. et al., 2013)
<i>Bacillus mycoides</i> , <i>Rhodococcus equi</i> , <i>Sphingomonas koreensis</i> , <i>Bacillus subtilis</i> , <i>Clostridium clostridioforme</i> , <i>Bacillus mojavensis</i> , <i>Pseudomonas alcaligenes</i> , and <i>Paenibacillus glucanolyticus</i>	Produces enzymes such as amylase, cellulase, proteinase, and lipase mainly involved in N cycling and mineralisation.	Velliangiri hill of Western Ghats in Tamilnadu	(Logeswaran et al., 2014)
<i>Micrococcus sp</i> NII-0909	Phosphorous (P) solubilization by release of organic acids	Forest soil of Western ghats	(Dastager et al., 2010)
<i>Gram negative, rod shaped Pantoea</i> NII-186	Phosphorous solubilization and Siderophore (Fe chelates) formation	Forest soil of Western ghats	(Dastager et al., 2009)
<i>Bacillus thioparus</i> NII-0902	Phosphorous solubilization and Siderophore (Fe chelates) formation	Forest soil of Western ghats	(Deepa et al., 2010)
<i>Pseudomonas sp.</i> , <i>Methylobacterium sp.</i> , <i>Bacillus sp.</i>	P solubilisation and siderophore formation	Western ghats for Karnataka	(S. P. Kumar et al., 2014)

Vesicular arbuscular mycorrhizal fungi (<i>Acualospora</i> , <i>Glomus</i> , <i>Sclerocystis</i> and <i>Scutellospora</i>)	P mobilisation	Western ghat forests of Tamil Nadu	(Muthukumar & Udaiyan, 2000)
Bacilli, Clostridia	Nitrogen cycling and decomposition of cellulose and starch	Malshej ghat	(Kuramae et al., 2012)
Streptomyces sp. and related actinomycetes	Produce antibiotics, vitamins, enzymes for mineralisation	Western Ghats soil, Tamil Nadu and Karnataka	(Devdass et al., 2016)
Nocardiopsis sp.	Produce antimicrobial compounds and antioxidants	forest soils in Western Ghats of Karnataka	(Salunkhe et al., 2023)
Proteobacteria, Firmicutes, Actinobacteria (general phyla)	Dominant bacterial groups involved in nutrient cycling, carbohydrate, protein, and lipid metabolism	Western ghats of MH	(Ghare et al., 2023)
Proteobacteria, Acidobacteria, Bacteroidetes	Carbon, nitrogen and sulphur cycling, polymer and organic matter degradation	Nilgiris region of WG	(Rohini-Kumar et al., 2013)

Genetic and metabolic pathways involved in nutrient bioavailability

Three theories have been proposed to explain how microbial activity can promote plant growth:

- (1) by manipulating the hormonal signalling of plants (Verbon & Liberman, 2016);
- (2) by repelling or outcompeting pathogenic microbial strains (Mendes et al., 2013);
- (3) increasing the bioavailability of soil-borne nutrients (Van Der Heijden et al., 2008).

The third mechanism by which soil bacteria break down resistant forms of soil-borne nutrients to release them for plant nutrition are the main topics of this review. Our goal is to

comprehend the role that bacteria play in plant nutrition as well as how plants modify their microbiome to optimize the nutritional advantages of this relationship.

Genetic pathways that code for nitrogenase enzymes, which transform atmospheric nitrogen (N₂) into ammonia, an accessible form, are involved in microbial nitrogen fixation. Microbial genes that encode phosphatases, which hydrolyze organic phosphorus molecules and release phosphate ions, increase the bioavailability of phosphorus. In a similar vein, microorganisms may mineralize organic sulfur molecules into sulfate thanks to sulfur cycling genes, which increases soil fertility. Microbial genetic expression and metabolic activity for optimal nutrient cycling are shaped by the composition of the microbial community, plant root exudates, and soil environmental variables (Fang et al., 2025).

Microbes alter soil micronutrients through intricate metabolic and genetic processes that control the biogeochemical cycling and micronutrient bioavailability. Microbial genes that encode metal transporters, redox processes, and electron transfer enzymes are associated with cycling of soil micronutrients such as iron (Fe), manganese (Mn), copper (Cu), zinc (Zn), molybdenum (Mo), and nickel (Ni). Fe and Mn, for instance, are necessary cofactors in microbial enzymes for redox reactions connected to the cycling of carbon, nitrogen, and sulfur such as breakdown of organic matter, nitrification, denitrification and sulphur oxidisation. Soil fertility and microbially driven nutrient turnover are influenced by genes engaged in these processes. By facilitating the uptake and efflux of micronutrients, certain microbial transporter genes control soil micronutrient availability and cellular homeostasis. To maximize microbial metabolic processes, regulatory genes react to the availability of micronutrients (Dai et al., 2023).

Through enzymatic processes including oxidation-reduction, chelation, and mineral solubilization, microbes propel changes in soil micronutrients. Enzymes that are dependent on copper and zinc are involved in metabolic processes and the oxidative stress response, which have an indirect impact on the cycling of nutrients. By interacting with macronutrient cycling routes such as the carbon and nitrogen cycles, microbial metabolism of micronutrients affects nutrient flux, pool sizes, and bioavailability to plants (Singavarapu et al., 2023).

Key microbial metabolic processes related to plant nutrition (Source: Jacoby et al., 2017)

Element	Biochemical processes	Microbial genes involved	Culture-independent literature	Culture dependent literature
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Nitrogen	Nitrogen fixation	nifD, nifH, nifK	(Xue et al., 2013)	(Bremer et al., 1990)
	Protein depolymerization	apr, npr, sub	(Rasche et al., 2014)	(Kohler et al., 2007)
	Urea catabolism	ureA, ureB, ureC	(Fierer et al., 2012)	(Kohler et al., 2007)
Phosphorous	Phosphate ester cleavage	phoA, phoD, phoX, ACPase, glpQ, ushA, appA, phyA, phyB	(Fraser et al., 2015)	(Kohler et al., 2007)
	Phosphate breakdown	phnJ, phnX	(Bergkemper et al., 2016)	
Sulphur	Sulphate ester cleavage	aslA, asfA	(Schmalenberger et al., 2008)	(Schmalenberger et al., 2008)
	Sulphonate breakdown	ssuD		(Kertesz, 2004)

Comparative Diversity Metrics

A direct comparison of quantitative metrics provides a clear picture of the disparity between the two land-use types. A meta-analysis confirmed that natural secondary forests consistently have higher microbial diversity than plantations. Fungal diversity, in particular, demonstrates the strongest response to land-use change, showing a greater decline in plantations compared to bacteria and actinomycetes (Pan et al., 2025). Similarly, Soil Microbial Biomass Carbon (MBC), a direct measure of the living carbon pool in the soil, is significantly higher in forest lands and sacred groves compared to paddy fields and cultivated areas, indicating a direct link between land use and the living component of soil health (Pradeepa et al., 2018).

The following table summarizes the key differences in microbial diversity and community structure.

Parameter	Forest Land	Agricultural Land	Sources
Shannon Diversity	High (4.72 ± 0.41 in mature forests)	Lower (4.18 ± 0.27 in middle-aged forests)	(Pan et al., 2025)

Fungal Diversity	Higher diversity, stronger successional response	Significantly lower, particularly in plantations	(Pan et al., 2025)
Fungal-to-Bacterial (F:B) Ratio	Higher	Lower due to tillage and fertilization	(Wang et al., 2025)
Microbial Biomass Carbon (MBC)	High (507.53 mg kg ⁻¹ in sacred groves)	Lower	(Pradeepa et al., 2018)
Community Structure	Complex, robust, highly connected networks	Simplified, more fragile networks	(Pan et al., 2025)
Dominant Phyla (Bacteria)	Acidobacteria, Proteobacteria, Actinobacteria	Proteobacteria exhibit higher relative abundance	(Hua et al., 2024)

Discussion

The Western Ghats region, with its altitudinal variety and climate heterogeneity, supports a complex soil microbiome. According to a thorough analysis of the aerobic bacterial diversity in the Northern Western Ghats (Maharashtra), Proteobacteria, Firmicutes, and Actinobacteria are among the dominating taxa with functional potential in the metabolism of carbohydrates, proteins, and fats. Altitude and soil physicochemical characteristics were associated with differences in the composition of microbial communities, indicating the impact of natural environmental gradients on microbial ecology (Ghare et al., 2023).

Significant antibacterial and antioxidant bioactive potentials have been shown by actinobacteria in the soils of the Western Ghats Forest, emphasizing their ecological significance and potential uses in biological technology. These microorganisms promote the operation of forest ecosystems by aiding in the biodegradation of organic matter and the cycling of nutrients (Siddharth et al., 2020). While agricultural and contaminated soils exhibited lower microbial biomass and diversity, comparative investigations across altitudes in forest environments revealed larger fungal and bacterial populations in undisturbed higher altitude soils. Microbial abundance

was also impacted by seasonal fluctuations; post-rainy seasons favoured higher microbial activity because of favourable moisture and temperature conditions (Kavitha et al., 2020).

The availability of nitrogen in soils is mostly determined by microbial nitrogen fixation, and changes in land use, such as the conversion of forests to agricultural land, have been observed to affect these communities. Crop productivity and soil nitrogen pools are impacted by decreased diversity and abundance of nitrogen-fixing bacteria in agricultural soils, highlighting the necessity of sustainable management techniques to preserve viable microbial populations (Shivakumar et al., 2020). Environmental factors also affect phosphorus solubilization by microbial phosphatases and organic acid producers. Mycorrhizal fungi work in concert to improve phosphorus uptake in the Western Ghats forest ecosystems, thereby promoting plant nutrition and soil fertility (Prakash Nayak et al., 2025).

For sulfur to be bioavailable, it must cycle through microbial sulfatases and sulphonate mineralization enzymes. These processes, which are impacted by environmental and land-use conditions, are mediated by soil microbial communities and have an impact on plant health and overall sulfur cycling. Microbial redox enzymes and metal transporters mediate the microbial transformations of micronutrients like Fe, Mn, Cu, and Zn, which are essential for nutrient cycling and preserving soil health (Paulraj et al., 2021).

These nutrient-solubilizing and converting bacteria can be found in microbial biofertilizers, which provide sustainable ways to improve soil fertility and lower the need for chemical fertilizer inputs. Nevertheless, additional field testing is required for these bioinoculants tailored to regional soil-microbe-plant systems (Chakraborty & Akhtar, 2021).

Our knowledge of the functional genes and pathways governing nutrient availability in soil microbes is constantly being expanded by molecular, metagenomic, and metabolomic approaches. These omics methods identify key microbial communities that preserve the nutrient balance of the ecosystem by revealing changes in microbial diversity and functional capacity with changes in land use (Wu et al., 2021).

Understanding how microbial genetic pathways work in situ for nutrient bioavailability requires a multidisciplinary approach that combines soil ecology, metabolic biochemistry, and microbial genetics. In order to reduce dependency on artificial fertilizers and support sustainable agriculture, this information can help guide initiatives to capture and improve beneficial microbial populations in agricultural soils (Hu et al., 2023).

Conclusion and Future Directions

The Western Ghats' agricultural and forest habitats have a noticeable impact on soil microbial diversity and the related nutrient solubilization processes. Compared to agricultural soils, which experience shocks and changed land management, forest soils generally support richer microbial communities with improved genetic potential and metabolic ability for nutrient cycling. Important insights into the dynamics of soil fertility can be gained by comprehending the microbial genetic routes for the cycling of nitrogen, phosphorus, sulfur, and micronutrients. Using metagenomic and multi-omics techniques opens up new possibilities for thoroughly describing these microbial functions.

Future Directions

- In order to understand the active microbial functional networks involved in nutrient bioavailability in the various Western Ghats habitats, future study should combine metagenomic, transcriptomic, and metabolomic data.
- The temporal stability and resilience of microbial functions under rapid land use change and climate conditions require longitudinal field research.
- Sustainable agricultural productivity could be increased by creating microbial consortia and bioinoculants that are specific to the local microbial populations.
- Additionally, integrating plant physiology and microbial nutrient cycling in the field will guide integrated nutrient management systems that maximize agricultural yields while preserving biodiversity.

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